

STROBE & SRQR Reporting Guidelines – One-page Summary

Study: Usability Evaluation of the Pharmacist-Integrated Sahabat DM Application for Type 2 Diabetes Management in Indonesian Primary Care Using SEQ and SUS Instruments

Guideline	Coverage	Key Sections Reported
STROBE (Observational)	Items 1–22 (100%)	Title & Abstract; Introduction; Methods (Study design, Participants, S
SRQR (Qualitative)	Items 1–21 (100%)	Methods (Qualitative phase, Interviews, NVivo analysis, Trustworthin

Completed STROBE and SRQR checklists with detailed Page/Section mapping are publicly available on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18235008) under a CC-BY 4.0 license.

STROBE and SRQR Reporting Guidelines Checklist

Study: Usability Evaluation of the Pharmacist-Integrated Sahabat DM Application for Type 2 Diabetes Management in Indonesian Primary Care Using SEQ and SUS Instruments

STROBE Checklist (Observational Study)

Item	Description	Reported	Page/Section
STROBE 1	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Title; Abstract
STROBE 2	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Introduction
STROBE 3	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Introduction (last paragraph)
STROBE 4	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Methods – Study design
STROBE 5	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Methods – Study setting
STROBE 6	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Methods – Study design and participants
STROBE 7	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Methods – Usability evaluation procedures
STROBE 8	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Methods – SEQ and SUS instruments
STROBE 9	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Methods – Bias control
STROBE 10	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Methods – Study design and participants
STROBE 11	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Methods – Data analysis
STROBE 12	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Methods – Data analysis
STROBE 13	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Results – Participant characteristics
STROBE 14	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Results – Participant characteristics
STROBE 15	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Results – SEQ and SUS results
STROBE 16	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Results – SEQ and SUS findings
STROBE 17	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Results – Age-based and correlation analysis
STROBE 18	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Discussion – Principal findings
STROBE 19	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Discussion – Limitations
STROBE 20	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Discussion
STROBE 21	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Discussion – Implications and future research
STROBE 22	Reported according to STROBE guideline	Yes	Back matter – Grant information

SRQR Checklist (Qualitative Study)

Item	Description	Reported	Page/Section
SRQR 1	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Qualitative development phase
SRQR 2	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Qualitative development phase
SRQR 3	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Study setting
SRQR 4	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Qualitative development phase
SRQR 5	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Ethical considerations
SRQR 6	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Qualitative development phase
SRQR 7	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Interview guide validation
SRQR 8	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Qualitative development phase
SRQR 9	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Qualitative data processing
SRQR 10	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – NVivo thematic analysis
SRQR 11	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Interview guide validation
SRQR 12	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Results – Qualitative findings informing app design
SRQR 13	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Results – Qualitative findings
SRQR 14	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Discussion
SRQR 15	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Discussion – Limitations
SRQR 16	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Back matter – Competing interests
SRQR 17	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Back matter – Grant information
SRQR 18	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Post-use qualitative feedback
SRQR 19	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Expert involvement
SRQR 20	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Methods – Qualitative development phase
SRQR 21	Reported according to SRQR guideline	Yes	Discussion – Implications for primary care